

**THE ISSUE OF EXPENDITURE IN THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM IN
THE KOKAND KHANATE**

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Abstract: In the article, the issue of the distribution of the financial system of the Kokand Khanate, i.e., the history of spending, is briefly presented. Data were compared to different sources using the method of comparative analysis.

Key words: Kokand, state, finance, cost, funds, ministry.

Information on the use of the treasury of the Kokand Khanate can be found in the researches of R. Nabiev and Z. Khatamova. While R. Nabiev mainly provided information about the period of Kokan Khan Khudoyor Khan, in the research of Z. Khatamova, you can find archival documents related to the administration of such khans as Olim Khan, Umar Khan, Mallakhon, Khudoyor Khan.

Kokan Khanate's office has a register of funds received into the treasury, as well as its expenditure is recorded in a separate register. According to the information contained in the documents stored in the UzMA, it is possible to find out information about the funds received by the treasury of the Kokand Khanate and their expenses.

According to A.P. Khoroshkhin, the person responsible for the amount of funds received in the treasury of the Kokand Khanate and their disposal was called mehtar. According to him, the mehtar, besides being the number one person in financial management, also had several other powers. Until 1865, the mehtar in the Kokan Khanate also served as a person who supplied the military with various

products. In 1866, as a report to the mehtar khan dealing with treasury affairs, the annual income of the state is 60,000 gold, but the actual income is 90,000 gold.

When it comes to the question of spending the treasury of the Kokand Khanate, it is known that the largest amount was spent on the military sector during the year. In times of war, the soldiers of the Kokan khans were under the care of regional or city governors. Their financial support was due to the fact that they were exempted from some state taxes.

In addition, according to Gaines, military taxes were collected from the population during times of war. Its amount was 5 gilts for rich people, and 2.5 gilts for middle-aged people.

It is known from sources that the palace library was rich in rare and valuable books. A large amount of money has been allocated from the treasury for books imported from foreign countries. In the documents, Mirza Muhammad Yusuf was given a wooden chest, white felt, three balls of cloth with flowers, and 8 coins to bring books to Kokan. Here it is said that the book was brought to the Khan's library. Because these documents were recorded by mirzas in the cabinet and preserved in the archive. Mulla Mirza Olim ibn Domla Mirza Rahim Tashkandi wrote in his work "Ansab-us salatin wa tawarikh-ul khawaqin" that the servants of the Russian king said that he should hand over 50 of the books left by the Khan, and he handed over only 10 books: fifty books, ten books without being able to place them perfectly, he drew a conclusion and gave me an answer" Mulla Mirza Olim lived during the reign of khans like Sherali Khan, Malla Khan, and Khudoyar Khan and in the early years of the occupation of the Russian Empire, and described the events of that period in his work as a person who saw them with his own eyes. . R. Nabiev stated that he may have been working as a librarian at the same time or as a librarian at the same time as the Russian government asked him to submit an account.

It should be noted that N. Pantusov wrote that the khan's military army in the capital was supplied from the water grown from the water of the Shakhrikhan canal dug during the reign of Umar Khan, that is, the information related to ____ years. Regarding the fact that during the time of Khudoyar Khan, a large amount of money was allocated from the treasury for the support of the army, "the amount of the grain tax collected from more than half of the 210 villages in the Koqan region was allocated for the financial support of the military unit."

A.Kun provides information about the financial support of officials in the form of products and money in the Ko'kan khanate. In it, the number of the father, qushbegi, parvanachi, dadho, biy, doorman, toksoba, mirokhor, guard, korchi, divachi, mirzaboshi, choraghas, batirs (military personnel) in the khanate and the annual grain products allocated to them are listed in the batman measure, and the money Funds are listed in silver coins for one year. A.Kun's information is extremely important in the study of the Kokan history financial system, and as a continuation of his work, R.Nabiev presented this information in the form of a table in his research. (Appendix 1.)

In A.Kun's information, the tarkhan, i.e., tax-exempt property of military personnel should not be mentioned. Because it is known that military officials who have tarkhan property were given pattas by the responsible officials. However, according to R. Nabiev, A. Kun's information is based on Tarkhan's property. In addition, A.Kun pointed out that he did not cite the source on which his information was based, whether it was taken from the records of the ministry or the information he spoke to the local people, he did not say anything about it.

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